

TRIAxIAL FAILURE CRITERIA FOR POLYMER COMPOSITES: PART (A) OF WWFE-II: COMPARISON BETWEEN THEORIES

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Abstract

This paper is concerned with providing a preliminary indication of the outcome of Part A of the 2nd World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE-II). The WWFE-II is an international activity aimed at assessing the maturity of established failure criteria capable of predicting the strength and deformation of materials under three dimensional (3D) or triaxial stresses. A comparison is made here between the theoretical predictions of twelve failure models, employed by their originators as a part of WWFE-II, to predict the complete failure envelopes and stress-strain curves under triaxial states of stress, using an identical input data. Various materials, lay-ups and loading conditions have been used in the analysis.

1. Introduction

Up to now, the predictive capability of current failure criteria for modeling deformation and strength responses of composite materials under three dimensional (3D) stresses has not been subjected to a thorough, independent and systematic assessment. Hence, the general validity of such 3D failure theories is currently in question.

The extensive work carried out in Ref[1] has identified a number of crucial gaps that have to be bridged in order to provide the designers of composites with confidence in the use of robust models for simulation. Among these gaps are:

- (1) The need to assess the current methodologies for triaxial failure criteria under 3D stresses.
- (2) The need to provide a state-of-the art assessment of the accuracy of advanced failure models based on damage, cracking and continuum mechanics principles.

Based on the proven philosophy that was adopted in Ref[1], the authors are currently coordinating a world study, known as the second World-Wide Failure Exercise (WWFE-II), to fill the gaps identified in order to increase the confidence in triaxial failure prediction methodologies, Ref[2].

The exercise is run in two stages, known as Part (A) and Part (B). Part A is devoted to comparing the predictions of competing theories and Part (B) is aimed at comparing the Part A predictions with available experimental data. As a result, a unique assessment of 12 failure criteria under three dimensional (3D) states of stress has been made in Part (A) of the WWFE-II. The originators (or their collaborators) of the 3D failure theories applied their methods 'blindly' to 12 carefully selected challenging problems (referred to as Test Cases), Ref[3]. These Test Cases involve various isotropic and fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) laminates (0° , $(0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ)_s$, $(\pm 35^\circ)_s$, and $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ laminates) subjected to a range of through-thickness and triaxial loading conditions. The Cases comprise the prediction of both failure envelopes and stress-strain curves at prescribed triaxial stress ratios.

Table 1 provides a list of the methodologies used. These methodologies are considered to be representative of the current modeling capabilities used by the composites community, including academia, designers and software houses. The models cover a wide range of methodologies, including micro-mechanics, physically-based analysis, interactive theories, numerically and analytically based methods, see Refs[4-15] for details.

Ref[16] summarises key features in each theory and these include: (a) Types of failure models employed, whether linear or nonlinear analysis was carried out, (b) Reliance on software and numerical methods, (c) Allowance for thermal stresses and (d) Identification of modes of failure.

Ref[16] contains an assessment of the theoretical results where failure envelopes and stress-strain curves were superimposed to show similarities and differences between the predictions of the various theories. In addition, bar charts were constructed to demonstrate the levels of agreement between the predicted failure stresses and strains. In this paper, selected results from the ‘blind’ theoretical predictions from 12 failure theories, making the backbone of Part (A) of the WWFE-II, are described.

2. Comparison between theories

In this section an overview of a subset of the WWFE-II results is presented to show the divergence in the predictions obtained from the 12 leading theories.

It must be noted that, due to a lack of space, it is not the aim of this paper to provide a comprehensive comparison between all the models for all of the challenging Test Cases. Readers are directed at other publications, Refs[4-16], to have an in-depth appreciation of the performance of the individual models and the performance of all of the models.

The comparison between the various models are described below in terms of (a) Predictions of the hydrostatic pressure of a multi-directional laminate (Test Case 8), see Figure 1, (b)- Predictions of biaxial compressive strength of a lamina Test Case 7), see Figure 2 and (c) Extreme predictions of a wide range of loading ratios, taken from the 12 Test Cases.

Figure 1 shows a bar chart describing the hydrostatic compressive strength (i.e. with a loading stress ratio: $-\sigma_x = -\sigma_y = -\sigma_z$) for Test Case 8 (angle ply glass/epoxy laminate subjected to three direct stresses as shown in the inset figure at the top right corner). The 12 models are labeled as A, B, C, ..., K and L. The high degree of variation in the strength prediction can be clearly seen where the ratio between the highest (theory labeled D) and the lowest (theory labeled L) predictions is, at least, 11.

Three of the models (A, B and C) predicted an open envelope for this loading case. It is clear from this graph and others that no two models gave identical predictions for all of 12 Test Cases. In particular, there was a lack of consensus regarding the effects of pressure on the elastic constants, strength behaviour and shear stress-stress curves of the composite lamina.

It is worth noting that, when the participants applied their theories to predict the strength of Test Case 1, (dealing with an epoxy or un-reinforced composite) under hydrostatic pressure ($-\sigma_x = -\sigma_y = -\sigma_z$), only two theories predicted closed envelopes and the other 10 theories predicted an open envelope at that stress ratio.

Figure 1: Comparison between the predictions of 12 failure criteria employed in Part A of the WWFE-II for predicting the triaxial (hydrostatic) compressive strength of Test Case 8, Ref[16].

Figure 2 shows another bar chart describing predictions of 12 models of the equi-biaxial compressive strength of a unidirectional lamina under transverse and through-thickness direct stresses (i.e. with a loading stress ratio: $-\sigma_2 = -\sigma_3$, $\sigma_1 = 0$, where directions 1, 2 and 3 coincides with fibre direction, transverse direction and through-thickness direction of a lamina). This biaxial loading ratio was taken from the 3D failure envelopes of Test Case 7. The models here are labeled as A1, B1, C1, ..., and L1, which are different to those in Figure 1. The ratio between the predictions of Model F1 and Model L1 is 13.5. Five of the models (A1 to E1) predicted an open envelope or a very large strength value at that loading ratio.

When the models A1 to L1 were employed to predict the hydrostatic compressive strength (i.e. with a loading stress ratio: $-\sigma_2 = -\sigma_3 = -\sigma_1$) of Test Case 7, a slightly different set of predictions was

obtained. While the trend observed in models A1 to D1 and I1 to L1 was the same as that in Figure 2, the rest of the theories (E1 to H1) gave dissimilar results to those in Figure 2. The implication of this opaque feature is that a user of a theory ought to make a pre-judgment or a conscious intervention as to which loading ratios are likely to produce unbounded or unlimited strength predictions.

Figure 2: Comparison between the predictions of 12 failure criteria employed in Part A of the WWFE-II for predicting the biaxial compressive strength in Test Case 7, Ref[16].

By taking into account those theories predicting an open or very large envelope, the above ratio would go up considerably.

Table 2 gives more details about the range of theoretical predictions of the various theories. In this table, 33 loading ratios (as listed in column 3) are selected from the results of the 12 twelve models to show the differences in the extreme predictions of these models. The loading ratios cover all the Test Cases, listed in column 2. For each of the loading ratios, the theories giving the highest and lowest prediction were identified, see columns 4 and 5. The ratio between the highest and lowest predictions is shown in the last column. A graphical representation of the data in the first and last columns is depicted in Figure 3.

For the data shown in Table 2, the following remarks may be noted

- The largest ratio occurs in Test Case 9 (between the prediction of Wolfe's theory and Christensen's theory) and is 24.
- The lowest ratio occurs in Test Case 10 (between the predictions of Hashin's theory and Tsai-Ha's theory) and is 1.9.
- Christensen's theory gave consistently the lowest predictions (12 out of the 33 loading ratios).
- Cuntze's theory gave consistently the highest

predictions (9 out of the 33 loading ratios).

3. Discussion and conclusions

- The overwhelming majority of theoreticians (9 out of 12) employed separate equations to delineate between isotropic and heterogeneous materials. This appears not to be an opaque feature of the models employed and rather it appears to require a conscious 'operator intervention' to make that selection, based on an examination of the problem to be analysed. This represents a peculiar difficulty to some of designers. Ideally, and from a designer's perspective, the preference would be for a 'black box' modelling tool that contains sufficient resilience to provide accurate predictions in all circumstances. The paper will attempt to point out at how the theories employed within WWFE-II could be made to satisfy that aspiration.
- There was significant diversity between the theoretical predictions in terms of whether or not the envelopes should be open under equal combined compressive through-thickness and transverse stresses and under equal triaxial compressive stresses.
- Full details of the performance of each of the theories and a comparison between the predictions of all the theories is presented by a special issue of Composites Science and Technology containing 15 papers, Refs[2-16]. The work reported in Ref[16] gives a thorough account of the essential lessons emerging from Part A of the WWFE-II, where a discussion is made regarding the sources of discrepancies between the predictions of the various 3D failure theories for predicting failure in a lamina and a lamina. Comparison between the theoretical predictions and available experimental data will be published shortly, in Part B of the WWFE-II. Hence, readers are advised to read Part B of the WWFE-II.

4. References

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- (*): Accepted for publication in Composites Science and Technology

Figure 3: A graphical illustration of the data shown in Table 1, showing the ratio of maximum to minimum predictions for 33 loading ratios (see Column 1 and Column 6)

Participants' Names	Organization	Approach represented	Theory
Bogetti, Staniszewski, Burns, Hoppel, Gillespie and Tierney[13]	U.S. Army Research Laboratory (USA)	3-D Maximum strain theory	Bogetti
Carrere, Laurin and Maire [10]	ONERA/DMSC (France)	Micromechanical based Hybrid Mesoscopic (MHM) 3D approach	Carrere
Cuntze [4]	Retired Engineer (Germany)	Failure mode concept (FMC) model	Cuntze
Huang, Jin, Ha and Tsai [15]	Hanyang University (S Korea), Stanford University (USA)	MicroMechanics of Failure (MMF) model	Ha-Tsai
Nelson, Hansen, Mayes [6]	Firehole Technologies, Wyoming University, Alfred University (USA)	Multi-continuum micro-mechanics (MCT) theory	Hansen
Zhou and Huang [12]	Tongji University (China)	Anisotropic plasticity and generalised max. stress	Huang
Kress [5]	ETZ Zurich (Switzerland)	Hashin's model	Hashin
Pinho, Darvizeh, Robinson, Schuecker, Camanho [9]	Imperial College (UK), University of Porto (Portugal)	3D physically-based constitutive model	Pinho
Deuschle and Kröplin [7]	ISD, Stuttgart university (Germany)	Puck's 3D- Physically based phenomenological model	Puck
Rotem [13]	Technion University (Israel)	Interactive matrix and fibre failure theory	Rotem
Zand, Wolfe, Butalia and Schoeppner [11]	Ohio State University, AFRL, Wright-Patterson, AFB, Ohio (USA)	Maximum strain energy method	Wolfe
Ye and Zhang[8]	Leeds University, Manchester University (UK)	Christensen's theory	Christensen

Table 1 A summary of participants and approaches represented in WWFE-II, Ref[16].

No	Test Case	Stress ratio	Theories predicting extreme values for final failure		
			Highest	Lowest	Ratio(*)
1	1	$\sigma_x: \sigma_y: \sigma_z = +1:+1:+1$	Bogetti	Carrere	6.94
2		$\sigma_x: \sigma_y: \sigma_z = -0.439:-1:-1$	Cuntze	Hashin	8.33
3	2	$\sigma_x: \sigma_y: \sigma_z: \tau_{xy} = -1:-1:-1:0$	Cuntze	Christensen	19.5
4		$\sigma_x: \sigma_y: \sigma_z: \tau_{xy} = +1:+1:+1:0$	Tsai-Ha	Hansen	3.1
5	4	$\sigma_x: \sigma_y: \sigma_z: \tau_{xy} = -600:-600:-600:\tau_{xy}$	Hashin	Huang	6.2
6		γ_{xy} Failure strain at -600MPa	Cuntze	Huang	9
7	5	$\sigma_1: \sigma_2: \sigma_3 = -1:-1:-1$	Cuntze	Christensen	12.3
8		$\sigma_1: \sigma_2: \sigma_3 = +1:+1:+1$	Bogetti	Hansen	3.16
9	6	$\sigma_1: \sigma_2: \sigma_3 = -1:-1:-1$	Cuntze	Bogetti	5.14
10		$\sigma_1: \sigma_2: \sigma_3 = 0:-1:-1$	Cuntze	Bogetti	9.16
11		$\sigma_1: \sigma_2: \sigma_3 = +4.7:+1:+1$	Bogetti	Christensen	12.95
12		$\sigma_1: \sigma_2: \sigma_3 = 0:+1:+1$	Tsai-Ha	Christensen	3.2
13	7	$\sigma_1: \sigma_2: \sigma_3 = -1:-1:-1$	Cuntze	Christensen	10
14		$\sigma_1: \sigma_2: \sigma_3 = 0:-1:-1$	Cuntze	Christensen	13.4
15		$\sigma_1: \sigma_2: \sigma_3 = +12.8:+1:+1$	Bogetti	Hansen	8.14
16		$\sigma_1: \sigma_2: \sigma_3 = 0:+1:+1$	Bogetti	Hansen	3.76
17	8	$\sigma_x: \sigma_y: \sigma_z = -1:-1:-1$	Cuntze	Christensen	11
18		$\sigma_x: \sigma_y: \sigma_z = +2:+1:+2$	Huang	Christensen	4.13
19		$\sigma_x: \sigma_y: \sigma_z = +1:0:+1$	Huang	Christensen	3.65
20		$\sigma_x: \sigma_y: \sigma_z = -1:0:-1$	Hansen	Tsai-Ha	3.5
21	9	$\sigma_x: \sigma_y: \sigma_z = -100:X:-100$	Wolfe	Christensen	2.13
22		Compressive Strain	Wolfe	Christensen	6.5
23		Tensile strain	Wolfe	Christensen	24 (A)
24	10	$\sigma_z: \tau_{xy} = 0:1$	Hansen	Tsai-Ha	2.15
25		$\sigma_z: \tau_{xy} = +1:0$	Hashin	Tsai-Ha	1.9 (B)
26		$\sigma_z: \tau_{xy} = -1:0$	Huang	Bogetti	2.87
27	11	$\sigma_z: \tau_{xy} = 0:1$	Hansen	Tsai-Ha	2.45
28		$\sigma_z: \tau_{xy} = +1:0$	Hashin	Tsai-Ha	2
29		$\sigma_z: \tau_{xy} = -1:0$	Huang	Bogetti	2.87
30	12	Compressive strength	Hansen	Tsai-Ha	10.5
31		Compressive strain	Hansen	Pinho	10.9
32		Tensile strain	Hansen	Tsai-Ha	12.3
33		Poisson's ratio	Rotem	Cuntze	7.4

(*)- These did not include values corresponding to those at section of open envelopes

(A): Highest ratio

(B): Lowest ratio

Table 2 Summary of theoretical results showing the range of final failure predictions for a large number of loading cases, Ref[16].